

**SUSTAINABILITY IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY
A STUDY OF NAGARKOT, NEPAL**

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Abstract: Sustainability is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland Report, 1987). Hotels today, being one of the important components of the Hospitality Industry, have been practicing sustainability by incorporating economic, environmental and social factors as outlined by Elkington (1994), universally known as the ‘triple bottom line’. To make it more realistic, hoteliers are intensifying the scope of sustainability by integrating corporate social responsibility (CSR) approach. However, a major challenge today is the people component to materialize all these practices and efforts. Attitude, resistance to change, irregular work hours, high physical and emotional work load and the perception of employees are the key factors to overcome in order to attain real green team and sustainable innovations in the Hospitality Industry. This paper offers an overview of the condition of sustainability efforts made by Hotels in Nagarkot, Nepal. Nagarkot is one of the important niche tourism destinations, having more than 50 hotels, lodges and eco-resorts, and it is about 32km north east of the capital city of Kathmandu. It is an eco-friendly tourism destination, famous among nature loving vacationers.

Keywords: Green team, Eco-resorts, Green buildings, Greenhouse gases

Sustainability and Sustainable Development

Before describing sustainability, it is indispensable to understand the history of sustainable development, sustainable tourism and how sustainability came to life in the field of development and academia. Although the term ‘Sustainable’ came out in 1987, through the Brundtland Report, the history of sustainability can be traced back to the 1960s. The conception of environmentalism gave birth to this thought in the 1970s (Bramwell & Lane, 1993, Hardy, Beeton & Pearson 2002, Kunwar, 2017, Liu, 2003, Kunwar, 2017) and in 1980s (IUCN1980, Liu, 2003) and finally it was recognized in the late 1980s and at the beginning of the 1990s. The Los Angeles times (1996) as cited by Dixon and Fallon (1989) also stated that the principle of ‘sustainable development’ derives from the discipline of economics that has been evolving for almost two centuries. The debate continues to focus on whether the Earth’s limited natural resources will continue to provide life support for humanity’s growing population.

It was Krippendorff’s seminal book *The Holiday Makers* (1984) (Franc, 2006, Kunwar, 2017) that introduced some of the most important ideas in tourism studies. After three years, the Brundtland Commission released its final report, ‘Our Common Future’ which famously defines sustainable development as: ‘the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs’ (Brundtland, 1987). As cited by Kunwar

(2017), sustainable development enhanced the concept of sustainable tourism development in 1992, founded by the Rio Conference in Agenda 21. So far as sustainable tourism is concerned, it is defined as a model form of economic development that is designed to improve the quality of life of the host community, provide a high quality of experience for the visitors and both of these maintain and depend on the quality of the environment. Wayne et. al., (2006) defined sustainability as a process that helps to create a vibrant economy and a high quality of life, while respecting the need to sustain natural resources and protect the environment. It expresses the principle that future generations should live in a world that the present generation has enjoyed but not diminished.

The concept of sustainable development is founded on three pillars commonly known as social, economic and environmental. In this regards Yadav (2016) highlighted sustainable development as an agent which reinforces the key development objectives of alleviating poverty, generating employment, redistributing income, empowering people and conserving the environment and natural resources. This reveals how sustainable development is important in developing countries. In the course of studying sustainable development, it is John Elkington who first coined the term 'the triple bottom line' in 1994 to these three pillars of sustainable development. His argument was that companies should be preparing three different (and quite separate) bottom lines; the traditional measure of corporate profit called the profit and loss account, a company's people account and planet account. The triple bottom line (TBL) thus consists of three Ps: profit, people and planet. It aims to measure the financial, social and environmental performance of the corporation over a period of time. Only a company that produces a TBL is taking account of the full cost involved in doing business (*The Economist*, Nov. 2009).

The Los Angeles times (1996), as cited by Basiago (1999), stated that more than half of the world's 6.6 billion people will be living in urban areas. This raises the prospect of crowded, violent and unhealthy cities threatened by the escalation of social conflict and intolerable environmental degradation, and the collapse of basic services. Sustainability is an ideal end-state. Like democracy, it is a lofty goal whose perfect realization eludes us. For this reason, there will always be competing definitions of sustainability. We know these definitions will always include the well-being of people, nature, our economy, and our social institutions, attained by working together effectively and over the long term (Allan, 1998).

Hospitality and Hotel Industry

Kunwar's (2017b), latest reviewed article shows that the question of hospitality has been raised by many scholars of hospitality and the tourism industry (Burgess, 1982, King, 1995, Jones, 1996a, Brotherton, 2013, Brotherton, 1999, Ottenbahcher, Harrington & Parsa, 2009, Selwyn 2013). Jones (1996a, p.6-7) has suggested that, 'there is certainly no commonly shared paradigm of what we mean by hospitality.....reference to the research literature would indicate that there has been little or no discussion of what we mean by hospitality... I would propose that the idea of hospitality research exists more in form than in substance.' Also, Taylor and Edgar (1996, p.218 &215), in reflecting on the current state of development of hospitality research, have pointed out 'An essential first step is to decide what the scope of hospitality research should be (and) if academic research in hospitality is to develop satisfactorily it is our view that it must do so within a coherent framework, (Kunwar, 2017b.). Chang, et. al., (2013) defined hospitality as an act of kindness in

welcoming and looking after the basic needs of customers or strangers, mainly in relation to food, drink and accommodation. A contemporary explanation of Hospitality refers to the relationship process between a customer and a host. When we talk about the 'Hospitality Industry', we are referring to the companies or organizations which provide food and/or drink, and/or accommodation to people who are 'away from home'. However, this definition of the 'Hospitality Industry' satisfies only a few situations.

This study has been confined to the hotel's hospitality provision and management, including sustainability in hospitality. Although there are various types of hotels in the world, this study focuses only on the green hotels, eco hotels, sustainable hotels and high-performance hotels where sustainable responsible tourist behaviour is highly expected. Recently, Kunwar (2017) has identified more than 23 types of hospitality and, in particular, two very important types (Persuasive Hospitality and Imposed Hospitality) which Nepalese people used before and after the Maoist movement (1996-2006). Nepal is now returning to persuasive hospitality. This study is based on hotel hospitality in the commercial domain.

Green Hotels, Eco Hotels, Sustainable Hotels and High-Performance Hotels

In recent years, the term sustainable hotel has been interchangeably used as green hotels, eco hotels and high-performance hotels. Dieneret, et.al., (2008, p.5) tried to give a new terminology for sustainability. The writers said: "Let us eliminate the phrase 'green construction' from our lexicon. Let us talk instead of 'smart building', 'high efficiency building', 'high performance building,' or simply 'the future of building. Certainly, this is not going to happen immediately". Michael (2008, p.1) says: 'There is no standard definition for green beyond its attachment to an eco-friendly business. Given the many building industry guidelines and the proprietary systems some hotel companies self-develop, being green can range from encouraging guests to reuse towels, to waste recycling, using wind electricity, to cooking with organic foods, to reducing carbon emissions, to installing rooftop solar panels. Compliance with various benchmarks can result in applying a green label.'

Hospitality Industry and Sustainability

Ryan (1991) as cited in Kunwar (2017a) has noted that tourists are strangers and bring with them the threat of social, cultural and environmental damage. "The tourist is not, however, simply a stranger, but a temporary stranger... they are guest, but an impersonal guest" (Kunwar 2017a). The consequences of this impersonality for hotel hospitality have been characterized by Wood (1994c) cited in Brotherton (2007) in terms of the mechanisms that hotels use to control their stranger-guests. The hospitality industry has increased steadily, growing by 17% between 2004 and 2014. According to the U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics 2015, it is estimated that there are 700,000 hotels in the world employing about 15.2 million people. The global hospitality market is generating revenue worth \$830 billion. Sustainability in the hospitality industry is one of the most important subsets of sustainable tourism development. Although sustainability in the hospitality industry is an important study, very few scholars of hospitality studies have given attention on this issue. However, some of eminent scholars of the hospitality industry have studied international leading hotels as a cosmopolitan hotel study, which cannot be compared with the small hotels run in the least developed countries. In fact, this kind of study will be very important

particularly in less developed country like Nepal. In the course of studying sustainability in the hospitality industry, Fotiadis (2015) and his comparative study of sustainability in small and medium-size hotels in Taiwan and Greece has provided the impetus for this study in Nagarkot.

Economic Sustainability in Hotels

It is important that the economic health of the organization should be the first priority, along with all the other operational activities. Social and environmental sustainability are interdependent with the economic health of the organization. In 1992, the Scandic Hotel U.S. was about to declare bankruptcy. Between 1990 and 1992, the hotel chain reported losses of approximately US \$50 million. A new CEO, Ronald Nilsson, was hired to produce a tremendous turnaround. Nilsson's prime agenda was to make the hotel environmentally sustainable. However, he realized that this goal was not possible unless the economic health of the hotel was improved (Cuenlla, 2002). Houdré (2008) believes that profitability is the key to sustainability which can be achieved by following the strict ethics, growing revenue and saving on costs, thus creating higher shareholder value. Michael et. al., (2008 p. 13) state: 'The negative environmental impact of an individual hotel is significant'. A hotel's operations require the generation of inputs and outputs that involve water, energy, chemical, food, sewage, and solid waste'.

Michael et. al., (2008) present some interesting facts about the U.S. Hospitality Industry, which spends about \$3.7 billion on energy, of which the electricity use is 60-70% of the total utility costs (electricity, water, fuel and gas). Guest lighting is about 30-40% of the hotel's electricity consumption. A typical hotel uses 218 gallons (1 gallon = 3.78 litres) of water per day per occupied room. Houdré (2011) in an advisory board meeting argued that hotels create a lot of waste and hence have a highly visible position in the community. A typical hotel releases between 160 and 200 kg of CO₂ per square meter of room floor area. Average energy consumption is 55 kwh per guest per night. Regarding waste, the average for a normal hotel is 1kg to 1.5kg waste per guest per night. A case study of the Scandic Hotels figures for 2012 showed: (i) an unsorted waste of 0.5kg per guest per night; (ii) energy consumption of 45.9kwh per guest per night; (iii) water consumption of 201.9 litres per guest per night, and (4) fossil carbon dioxide of 1.9kg per guest per night (Cuenllas 2012).

Burns et. al., (2015) discusses the best practices to be found in the world's hotels. Given that the electricity consumption in a hotel accounts for 60-70% of the total energy cost, a 10% reduction in the energy cost results in an increase in average room rate by \$1.35. Again, reducing the water consumption by 7% results in a saving of \$135000 to \$218000 in the natural gas bill per year used to heat water. Solar energy can be the best way to cut down the cost while using 'green' energy. Solar energy implementation can save on average 25% of the energy that a hotel needs to operate. This accounts for saving of 155kwh of electricity per year. Although this practice has not been widely adopted, switching to an air-to-water heat pump from a conventional heating system (typically, heat from electronic sources or a condensing boiler) can save 50 percent of the energy used and reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 12,000 kg. Where natural gas is available, hotels can replace electricity with gas as a source of energy for the laundry and catering services, reducing the hotel's environmental impact.

After receiving two consecutive awards in 2005 and 2006, Marriott International Hotel worldwide improved its energy management which helped it to save \$6 million and at the same time reduced

its greenhouse gas emissions by 70,000 tons. The programme included the installation of 450,000 compact fluorescent light bulbs (CFLs), conversion of all outdoor signage to LED and fiber optic lighting, and implementation of energy and water efficient laundry systems. Through its reduction in energy consumption, Marriott's efforts represent a 2 percent greenhouse gas reduction per room. In 2004, the historic Willard InterContinental in Washington, DC, installed CFLs in common areas and guest rooms. According to hotel management, guest complaints of lighting quality have decreased. As a result of this upgrade, which paid for the initial investment in less than six months, the hotel is saving one million kilowatt hours and more than \$100,000 annually. Fifty-three hotels installed building automation in 2013, and realized nearly \$200,000 in savings by year-end (Marriott Sustainability Report, 2014)

Environmental Sustainability in Hotels

The Rio Conference (1992) encouraged the hospitality industry to take environmental initiatives such as, the first environmental certificate programmes and initiatives to build so called green buildings. In the 2000's environmental issues were incorporated in the wider concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (Goldstein & Primlani, 2012). Even though hoteliers are considering the social aspects of their operations these are less developed than the environmental aspects (Van Rheede & Blomme, 2012). Basiago (1999) stated that 'Environmental sustainability' requires maintaining natural capital, as a provider of economic inputs called 'sources', an absorber called 'sinks' and of economic outputs called 'wastes' (Daly 1973 & 1974; World Bank 1986; Pearce & Redclift 1988; Pearce et. al. 1990a & 1990b).

Bruns-Smith et. al., (2015 p. 2) states that 'Hilton set a goal of reducing waste by 20 percent and water use by 10 percent by the end of 2013. Hilton exceeded those goals, reducing waste by 24.9 percent and water reductions by 10.2 percent. (The firm's energy and carbon reduction goals proved more elusive.) Thus, decreasing water and energy use can cut utility costs for a hotel while also showing its commitment to corporate stewardship and decreasing its drain on the surrounding environment'. Marriot's Sustainability Report (2014) states that Marriott has been operating with responsible management of resources and has established a formal program to reduce water and energy use. With the rise in unpredictable weather patterns, and global warming conditions, Marriott stresses natural capital and resources, and air and water quality issues. Marriott has the further goals of reducing water consumption by 20% by 2020; empowering hotel development partners to build green hotels, to educate and encourage guests and associates to conserve and preserve resources, and to innovatively control resources including rainforest protection and water conservation.

Social Sustainability in Hotels

Compared to economic and environmental sustainability, social sustainability has not been understood and is least well defined. It has received less attention in public discourse even though it is an important pillar of overall sustainable development. McKenzie (2004) defines social sustainability as the formal and informal processes, systems, structures and relationships which actively support the capacity of current and future generations to create healthy and socially sustainable communities that are equitable, diverse, connected, democratic, and provide a good quality of life.

Bukhari (2012) says: “Social capital and community infrastructure building are another important construct of social sustainability in hospitality industry, which by the results we see lie below in comparison to ‘engaged governance’ and ‘social justice & equity’ as these are the basic services, which one organization provide and make available in retort to the demands of communities”. Bukhari highlighted about the importance of these two components to enhance the quality of life by building networking, norms, trust, health measures, education, transportation, and rural development. Over all, these elements need to be further focused and developed in the selected organizations.

Houdré (2008) states that the Taj Hotels Group, one of the multi-billion-dollar subsidiaries of Tata Group, has a long history of serving women, artisans and the education of the children. Employees and the corporate officers actively participate in various social activities via the 30% of total profit after tax of the company. Taj Hotels believe in what Mahatma Gandhi has said about the earth: ‘The Earth provides enough to satisfy every man’s needs, but not every man’s greed.’ Taj Hotels are involved in sustainable development via corporate governance, employee relations, environmental protection, and community services via the Tata Council for Community Initiatives, which embraces social development, environmental management, biodiversity restoration and employee volunteering. In 2008 Taj announced its newest programme, EARTH (Environment Awareness & Renewal at Taj Hotels), a project which reiterates the conscious effort of one of Asia’s largest and finest group of hotels to commit to energy conservation.

Marriott International Hotels with 4000 hotels worldwide in 80 different countries have been innovatively working to make it understand that conservation and community engagement is more than a moral imperative. Marriot also believes that socially responsible business makes good business sense, building customer preference and loyalty. It also believes that travellers also care about hotels that advocate issues of global importance. It has taken initiatives in preserving the Amazon rain forest, providing job readiness training to underserved youth, advocating for secure and easy visa policies into the US (Marriot 2014, Sustainability Report). Willard Intercontinental Hotels, USA are involved in international causes, reinforcing the reality that the U.S. is a generous and caring country. Helping children internationally means supporting such diverse causes as access to clean water in Africa and offering aid to victims of the Asian tsunami (Hourde, 2008).

Research Methodology

The study for this paper was carried out with the help of a structured questionnaire, as well as unstructured questions to as many as 30 hotels and eco resorts in Nagarkot with their 100 in-house guests and about 100 staff. Ten students of the Asian Institute of Technology and Management spent approximately a week in Nagarkot and, together with the researcher, administered the completion of the structured questionnaire by general managers, owners, staff, local stakeholders and guests. The study also consulted a range of source material comprising around seventy journal and magazine articles, ‘write-ups’ by some eminent personalities, books, soft copies of e-articles.

The Hotel Industry in Nepal

After the advent of democracy in Nepal, the hotel industry started developing at a noble pace. Hotel Himalaya Inn opened in 1950 followed by Hotel Paras in 1951, Hotel Nepal in 1953, Hotel

Snow View in 1955, hotel Shankar in 1964, Hotel Annapurna, a five-star deluxe hotel in 1965, Hotel Soaltee Oberoi 1966, Blue Star Hotel in 1968, Hotel Crystal in 1972, Hotel Yak and Yeti in 1973, Hotel Radisson in 1998 and hotel Hyatt Regency in 2000. Currently there are eight five-star hotels and about twenty-four-star hotels in Nepal. A total of 2500 hotels are registered with the Hotel Association of Nepal and about 350,000 people are employed by these hotels (HAN 2016). A forecast that a number of new airports will open around the country has led to the expectation that 20 or more five-star hotels, 40 four-star and about 70 three-star hotels will open by 2020.

This is however, a very small volume in comparison to a global volume of 700,000 hotels in the world. However, for a small country like Nepal, it is regarded as a positive growth, a 10% turnover rate every year. Rai (2012) states that Nagarkot, having about 50 tourist class hotels, lodges and eco-resorts is one of the important niche tourism destinations which is about 32 km north west of the capital city Kathmandu. It is an eco-friendly destination famous for nature loving vacationers. Nagarkot is situated at about 7,200 feet and is known for its beautiful views of the sunrise over the eastern Himalayas. Nagarkot as a countryside capital is very much a resort village, where people come to escape the sweltering heat of the city and stay overnight. The overall capacity of all the establishments is 603 rooms and 1288 beds. The average expenditure of an individual tourist per stay is \$75. According to Rai (2012), the 32 establishments in which he had researched, employed 453 staff members, of which 88% are males and 12% females. On an average, females are paid 2.9% less than their male co-workers. During the peak months, 40% of total expenditure on purchase of food items is spent in periphery 3, 45% in periphery 2 and 15% in periphery 1. For slack months the share of purchase is 35%, 51% and 14% for periphery 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Findings and Discussions

In an economic sustainability analysis, it is seen that the hoteliers in Nagarkot are aware of guest participation in sustainability. 33% of the total hotels requested their guests to control the use of water and reuse towels and 70% of guests accepted the request. This is similar to what Bruns-Smith et. al., (2015) found in their study in the top 100 resorts in USA, where about 20 environmentally sustainable resorts have towel and linen re-use programme in place and 80% of the customers happily participated. Guests are also requested to use electricity wisely in terms of using electrical appliances such as heating, lighting, ventilations, air-conditioning and televisions, etc. Some hotels also engage their guests in community services.

The majority of visitors like the design of the hotels they are staying in. This indicates that the designs of the hotels at Nagarkot are eco-friendly and have sustainability components installed. Hotels at Nagarkot reflect Nepali culture and ethnicity, but the majority of hotels are modernised to harmonise with the needs of a modern traveller. It is also found that the majority of guests are willing to spend more on eco and environment-friendly hotels. This is consistent with the findings of the Trip Advisor global survey (2006) as cited in Diener (2008, p. 15), which showed that 34% of guests were willing to pay more for environmental friendly hotels. It is observed that the guests also want to be the part of the hotel and contribute something to the society, locals, environment, community and nature. We figured out that the half of the employees are engaged in any particular hotel for less than a year while only 2% employees are engaged in a particular hotel for more than 15 years. It also shows that most of the employees are temporary and are not familiar to their

workplace which might also result to lack of loyalty and easy acceptance to the development programmes like sustainability.

The majority of employees believe controlling expense is the key to cost control like avoiding unwanted cost, recycling and reusing methods, controlling food waste and managing energy, electricity and saving fuels are the fundamentals in controlling cost. It was also found that owners are the most concerned stakeholders in the hotels about the costs and profitability but because of awareness issues and some training and development condemnns, it is difficult to get what is expected from the operations. The survey clearly shows that the majority of the employees have not received any training programme on sustainability yet. It clearly indicates the practice of sustainability is not well executed in Nagarkot till date. Employees and hoteliers are not well aware about the sustainability trainings while few employees have received training on the sustainability, and yet it needs to be implemented. We asked employees on what conditions will they be happy to participate in training and development programs in sustainability issues apart from another skills training? Surprisingly, the data showed that 60% of the employees will take part because they want to acquire knowledge about the subject, and only 20% will take part if the hotels share them the direct enticement from the gains (bonus, incentives, etc.) by implementing the sustainability programmes. The rest will be happy to take part in the sustainability training programme if their hotel gains more profit. When asked about what the tools are the hotel owners and managers apply to control the cost of the hotel, most of them said they used LED bulbs instead of florescent and incandescent. We also got other answers like effective use of raw materials, use of local products, etc. This shows that the people are aware of sustainability components in their own way and this further needs a structured sustainable hotel development plan for achieving the sustainable goals of the hotels in this region.

Fig. 1. An overview of sustainable practices of hotels in Nagarkot, Nepal

While inspecting on the food cost that the hotels incur on a monthly basis, it is seen that the hotels are able to maintain their food cost percentage in between 20-32%, which is an ideal figure (Tilly 2014). It is found that out of as many 40 books and journals referred for his study, none of the scholars precisely talked about food cost and its relationship with economic sustainability. Out of total food and beverage revenue, 28%-32% goes in food cost and if controlled properly, 1% reduction in food cost can save as much as 10% saving in electricity cost of the hotel. In Figure 1, it is seen that 40% of the total hotels surveyed are managing the waste in a way of converting it to compost for flower gardens and for farming vegetables for their own use. Recycling is the process of converting waste materials into new materials and objects. It is an alternative to ‘conventional’ waste disposal that can save material and help lower greenhouse gas emissions. Recycling can prevent the waste of potentially useful materials and reduce the consumption of fresh raw materials, thereby reducing: energy usage, air pollution, and water pollution. We found a part response for each category about 50% said yes and the remaining 50% said no. From a survey on source of water in the hotels it is seen that most of them use spring water. 63% of respondents admit that they use spring water for their daily use because of the ample availability of natural springs in the area. Only 33% of respondents have a rain water harvesting system in practice. On the other hand, 67% do not know the benefit of a harvesting system. From the above data 53% respondents said that no one in the hotel is deputized to look sustainability concept. Remaining the 16% are owners themselves. Sustainability is a balancing act, hence needs a participatory act. Sustainability has become a far-reaching field, covering a range of environmental and social issues. We found an overwhelming response of in-house vegetable farming. 79% respondents said that they have their own in-house vegetable farms for the guests

and production is organic in nature. It is also found that some of them are considering the organic farming in the near future. 95% of hotels use chemical products for cleaning purposes and rest of the used herbal soap. The reason is because of non-availability of the green products though the hotels want to use. 70% respondents are not being able to use because of non-availability of the products. Whereas 20% of them said the green cleaning products are not much affordable.

Fig. 2. An overview of sustainable components of Hospitality industry in the world

Figure 2 is an outcome of the study and understanding of the sustainability components in hotel industry in a nutshell. It is believed that this diagram will be helpful for the scholars and researchers to have a quick understanding of what is expected out of being sustainable hotel industry.

Conclusion

The origin of sustainability may date back to 100 years ago from an idea known as spaceship earth (George 1879/2009, in Alhaddi 2015, 6). Sustainability practice is a healthy and long-term practice in today for a secured tomorrow. Hotels in the world are practicing sustainability knowingly or unknowingly incorporating around 40%-50% of the sustainability components in their daily operations. A study in a small cluster of hotels like Nagarkot, Nepal outlines that sustainability should be a global practice from cosmopolitan to provincial to the last resorts in a global world of hotels. Here the term cosmopolitan hotels refer to the hotels located in the diverse multicultural cities; provincial refers to a small countryside hotel industry and the last resort represents the hotels which are located both in humans and non-human habitations. Be it green, eco, and high performance or sustainable the universally accepted components to achieve real time sustainable goal of any hospitality business is reliant on three key elements namely: economic health, social health and environmental health components. It is the difference of revenue and cost factors which determines the thickness of hotel's economic sustainability in which the social and environmental sustainability practices can cultivate. However, it is important that all three components should work simultaneously to give a perfect balance.

The recent article on environmentally sustainable tourist behaviour by Juvan and Dolnicar (2016) suggests continuing the work on different environmental tourist behaviour dimension one of the dimensions of sustainability and this study encourages the future researchers to study about the environmentally sustainable behavior of the tourists in the host country to bring a complete balance towards the holistic sustainable of the hotel industry.

From the study, it has been identified that approximately 93% of hotels are practicing sustainability concept knowingly or unknowingly the exact meaning of sustainability. Similarly, it has been found that 34% of the guests are willing to pay more for the hotels which are environmentally sustainable. Another finding from the study suggests that the guests are happy to participate in the sustainable development practices of the Hotels. One of the key findings shows that from the employees' perspective, 60% employees basically take part in the sustainable development trainings and workshops to gain more knowledge from the program, which is a positive indicator of learning and development.

Because of the not having any planned sustainable development practices implemented in the Hotels in Nagarkot, researchers faced lots of challenges on gathering the required data. The questions asked to the respondents were further broken down into smallest parts to explain the outcomes expected from the question. Another limitation of the study was the distance of the hotels/resorts from one another which took lots of time for the study.

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